

The Cult of Maritime Hera

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Greek Religions, Hellenistic Religions, Ancient Mediterranean, Roman Religions, Levantine Religion, Indo-European Religion, Rome, Greek Cult, Women's Spirituality, Phoenician Cult, Religious Practice, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult

The aim of this entry is to shed light on a largely unknown facet of the religious veneration of the Greek goddess, Hera. Evidence for Hera being worshipped as a goddess of the sea is derived from an interdisciplinary approach; the votive assemblages from her sanctuaries, of which at least 7 are seaside, her symbolic and material connections to the sea and water, and myths she is involved in. As a goddess of the sea, Hera was the recipient of at least 46 ship models discovered in a religious context and hundreds of other votives associated with maritime imagery. It is clear that she was worshipped in practical matters of seafaring, such as being prayed to for a safe journey or ideal weather conditions. However, there is also evidence for her maritime cult in a broader, instinctual, symbolic connection with the sea, related to aspects of creation, motherhood, liminality, and transitional spaces.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 400 BCE

Region: Sanctuaries and Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Region tags: Greece, Italy, Aegean, Northern Greece, Central Greece, Peloponnese, Naples, Magna Graecia, Corinth, Argolid, Thrace, Western Greece, Dodecanese, Northern Aegean Islands, Lesbos, Samos, Corfu (Kerkyra), Sardinia, Etruria

Locations of Hera sanctuaries associated with the maritime cult are widespread throughout Greece and Italy. Material and/or physical evidence is attributed to at Argos, Perachora, Samos, Tiryns, Corfu, Corinth, Gravisca, Kroton, Olympia, Poseidonia (both Foce del Sele and Paestum), and Thrace.

Literary implications for the cult of Maritime Hera also exist at Boeotia (Aidepsos, Chalkis, Eretria, Karystos) Lesbos, Sardinia, and Cyrene.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Jens David Baumbach, *The Significance of Votive Offerings in Selected Hera Sanctuaries in the Peloponnese, Ionia, and Western Greece*.

Notes: Baumbach's publication was of utmost value to my research of Hera. While he focuses on other aspects of Hera's cult worship, his compilation and description of votives (and using them as an analytical tool of their own) was significant to my findings. His bibliography also provided guidance of where to look next for analyses of Hera.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

— Source 1: Paul Forsythe Johnston, *Ship and Boat Models in Ancient Greece*. Annapolis, Md.: Naval Institute Press, 1985 (also available online in some institutions). Paul is the earliest author in my research to explicitly state that Hera may have been a patron deity of sailors. He compiled a list of ship models found throughout Greece (although not all relevant to this research are listed there).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Online sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1 URL: <https://era.library.ualberta.ca/items/5aa6db65-9fe5-4122-b57f-06893aca2fa6>

— Source 1 Description: *Hera Maritima: Exploring Hera as a Goddess of the Sea*. This is my masters thesis, which is a full exploration of the subject of Hera's maritime cult and worship. <https://doi.org/10.7939/r3-9k2x-p286>

Notes: My extensive bibliography, as well as pages 13-17, outline the most valuable sources which begin to shed light on Hera's maritime aspect and its recognition (or lack thereof).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

– Source 1 URL:

https://library.oapen.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.12657/37993/9789004314832_webready_content_text.pdf;jsessionid=871E2899091083/sequence=1

– Source 1 Description: Deborah Boedeker, "Hera and the Return of Charaxos." In *The Newest Sappho* (link provided, also available in print). Boedeker recognizes both physical and literary evidence for Hera's maritime worship and mentions many sites where she may have received this worship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: This cult was widespread and in my opinion, in part developed due to colonization and the consequences of sea travel, particularly between Greece and Italy and Greece and the Eastern Aegean. Not only was Hera a goddess of traditional marriage, but also the 'marriage' between regions. It is fitting for her to oversee the travel from one place to another, and have power over the water they travel on. There are also similarities between the maritime cult of Hera and the cult of Poseidon (votive finds, locations of sanctuaries, links to creation/earth and sea).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: It is important to note that the cult of maritime Hera is not uniform, nor is it one particular group, or even the same in each location there is evidence for this kind of veneration. It is a subset of the general worship of Hera as a goddess, appealing to one of her aspects and realms, that could be known by and appealing to a number of people with varying motivations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does the religion have official political support

– I don't know

Notes: Greek religious worship in general was supported politically and not separated from politics of society; the cult of maritime Hera was no exception.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: The cult of maritime Hera would have primarily involved the practices and religious worship of seafarers. This could include those who went to sea for practical or every day reasons such as fishing, however, it could involve multiple classes of people. They could be soldiers, artists, colonizers, families of the elite, or specialized craftsmen, to name a few. I also believe the cult of maritime Hera was derived from larger religious implications and realms Hera would have been involved in; thus, many would have known or participated in the religious practices, and the number of people in this religious group could be incalculable.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

— Yes

Notes: Monumental religious architecture (temples dedicated to Hera) are present at many of the cult sites of Maritime Hera: Samos, Greece - the largest Greek temple ever built Argos, Greece - The Argive Heraion Perachora, Greece - The Heraion at Perachora Corfu, Greece - 610 BC Temple characterized as a Heraion Corinth, Greece - temple to Hera 5km south of Corinthian harbour Gravisca, Greece Kroton, Italy (3 temples) Lesbos, Greece (possible temple structure, still under debate) Olympia, Greece - Heraion Poseidonia, Italy Paestum Italy

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

— I don't know

Notes: The temples were located within sanctuaries and would have been the main attraction other than the altar, where votives would have been presented. Typically, the larger the temple, the larger the sanctuary. If I were to estimate, perhaps 10-20% of the sanctuary space could be used by the temples.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

—Square meters: 5513

Notes: It was 105 m long and 52.5m wide. First monumental Ionic temple at Samos, Greece. 570-540 BC. 2:1 ratio of length. Double row of columns (dipteros). Polykrates was the tyrant of Samos at the time, and Rhoikos was the architect.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

—Height, meters: 20

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Tombs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: 2 life-size ship bases at Samos and a ship dedication near the altar of Samos.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

Notes: Inside the sanctuaries of Hera noted in region above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

— Yes

Notes: Hera is known to show herself as a peacock, or have peacocks next to her in imagery. The peacock's sound was known to indicate weather changes, which is connected to Hera's power over the sea and elements. Samian coins have been found with iconography of nude infants, a temple, and peacocks.

Reference: Bardis, Panos D.. "Heavenly Hera Heralds Heroines: Peace Through Crosscultural Feminist Symbols and Myths". *International Journal on World Peace* 5, no. 4 (1998): 89-111.

Reference: O'Brien, Joan V.. *The Transformation of Hera: A Study of Ritual, Hero, and the Goddess in the Iliad*. Maryland: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers Inc., 1993.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

— Yes

Notes: Part of Hera's religious power over the sea is derived from her identification as a mother goddess. Mother goddesses are equated with the earth and the sea, and I believe some of the iconography and votive objects found in her cult sites relate to this aspect (i.e., little goddess figurines holding ships, models of houses or temples). This is further explored in my thesis listed above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

— Yes

Notes: Hera is identifiable as a female goddess, typically wearing a crown and holding a sceptre. She is sometimes accompanied by a male consort, or animals such as lions, peacocks, birds, or cows.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Humans:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Other features of iconography:

— Yes

Notes: There are many notable objects dedicated as votive offerings in sanctuaries of Hera related to her maritime cult (these all contain ship and sea iconography, or are representations of ships themselves). Votive ship models were found at Argos (1), Perachora (1), Samos (40), Tiryns (1), Corinth (17 - related to both Aphrodite and Hera), Gravisca (1), Olympia (2), and one is noted at Sardinia but it is not documented formally. Life-size ship dedications and ship bases have been found at Samos (9 bases at Samos, 1 ship near the altar). Female figurines with flower-decorated ships either at their shoulders, at the base, or in their hands have been found at Argos (2), Perachora (1), and Tiryns (2-6, number debated). Additionally at Tiryns, in a hoard of over 2000 figurines, it is noted that many of them include a flower-decorated base which could have been mounted on a ship. Vessel fragments depicting or in the shape of ships have been found: Argos (2 vase paintings and 1 pouring vessel in the shape of a ship), and Perachora (1 - a cup depicting two ships surrounding by dolphins). Seals and seal-rings have been found depicting boats: (Tiryns, 1 gold-seal ring complete with an enthroned goddess next to a ship), 4 egyptian seals with boats and one with a man in a boat at Tiryns as well. Coins with representations of ships have been found at Samos as well, where Hera was the patron deity. In addition to ships, notable maritime-related finds include: -pieces of coral, some of which are amuletic and some are not (at Argos, Perachora, Samos, Foce del Sele, Paestum). -mini terracotta hydriai, meant to ask for rain in times of drought (Argos - several hundred of them) -images of fish, sirens, dolphins, waves on vessels, altars, cups attested to at multiple sites -conical cups, meant to be sunk and determine whether a sea voyage will be safe or not, at multiple sites -shells, anchors, and fish hooks (Perachora, Kroton, Foce del Sele)

Reference: Baumbach, Jens David. *The Significance of Votive Offerings in Selected Hera Sanctuaries in the Peloponnese, Ionia, and Western Greece*. Oxford: BAR Publishing, 2004.

Reference: Waldstein, C, Rufus Byam, A Lythgoe, Norton R Morton, H De Cou, T. Woolsey Heermance, J. Clark Hoppin, et al.. *The Argive Heraeum Vols 1 and 2*. American School of Classical Studies at Athens. Archaeological Institute of America (190205). Boston; Cambridge:: Houghton, Mifflin and Company; The Riverside Press, 1905.

Reference: Wachsmann, Shelley. *Seagoing Ships & Seamanship in the Bronze Age Levant*. College Station: Texas A&M University Press, 1998.

Reference: Johnston, Paul Forsythe. *Ship and Boat Models in Ancient Greece*. Annapolis, Md: Naval Institute Press, 1985.

Reference: Payne, Humfry, T.J. Dunbabin, and Alan Albert Antisdell Blakeway. *Perachora, the Sanctuaries of Hera Akraia and Limenia: Excavations of the British School of Archaeology at Athens. 1930-1933. Vol 1.* Oxford: The Clarendon Press, 1940.

Reference: Payne, Humfry, T.J. Dunbabin, and Alan Albert Antisdell Blakeway. *Perachora, the Sanctuaries of Hera Akraia and Limenia: Excavations of the British School of Archaeology at Athens. 1930-1933. Vol 2.* Oxford: The Clarendon Press, 1962.

Reference: Kyrieleis, Helmut. "The Heraion at Samos". In *Greek Sanctuaries: New Approaches*, edited by Nanno Marinatos and Robin Hägg. London: Routledge, 1993.

Reference: Hans, Walter, Angelika Clemente, and Wolf Dietrich Niemeier. *Ursprung Und Frühzeit Des Heraion Von Samos. Samos 21.1.* Deutsches Archaologisches Institut, 2019.

Reference: Ringheim, Hannah L.. "Hera and the Sea. Decoding Dedications at the Samian Heraion". *Study Hercynia XXIII*, no. 1 (2019): 11-25.

Reference: Brüggemann, Nora. *Kult Im Archaischen Tiryns : Eine Analyse Neuer Befunde Und Funde, Tiryns Vol. 18*, 2015.

Reference: Papademetriou, Alkestis. *Tiryns: A Guide to Its History and Archaeology*. Athens: Hesperos Editions, 2015.

Reference: Kyrieleis, Helmut. *Anfänge Und Frühzeit Des Heiligtums Von Olympia: Die Ausgrabungen Am Pelopion 1987-1996*. Berlin; New York: Walter De Gruyter, 2006.

Reference: Demetriou, Denise. *Negotiating Identity in the Ancient Mediterranean: The Archaic and Classical Greek Multiethnic Emporia*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012.

Reference: Boardman, John. *The Greeks Overseas: Their Early Colonies and Trade*. New York: Thames and Hudson, 1999.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: At sanctuaries noted previously and in the region section.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in a largely symbolic way. Hera is connected with heroes and is the guardian of many heroes who take voyages, both symbolically and practically. In literature, she is involved with guiding a few chosen young men (Jason, for example) on journeys which ultimately occur on the sea and end with them becoming mature men, often married men. I believe this aspect which occurs in literature and myth stems from her religious involvement in the journey from youth to maturity, with the end goal as marriage (for both men and women) She oversees this 'journey' from start to finish.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

→ How strict is pilgrimage:

– I don't know

Notes: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: There is an association between the sea, female deities, ships, and death. In archetypal research, it has been said that the sea was considered the 'mother,' and the dead should be brought back to her, fulfilling the circle of life and death. The sea is also a liminal space, beyond human reach, as curious and mysterious as death (and has been quoted as the female lap/bosom). Hera's power over the sea can be related to death and the afterlife in this way. She has oracular associations, evidence for chthonic libations at her sanctuaries, and her temple at Perachora was known as the tomb of Medea's children. The cult of maritime Hera could very well have been connected to beliefs of death and the afterlife on a more symbolic and archetypal level. It is also interesting to note that Hera is a goddess of fertility and birth, and birth/death are extremely interconnected in Greek religion in general.

Reference: Lindenlauf, Astrid. "The Sea as a Place of No Return in Ancient Greece". *World Archaeology* 35, no. 3 (2003): 416-33.

Reference: Fee, Christopher R, and David Leeming. *The Goddess: Myths of the Great Mother*. London: Reaktion Books, 2016.

Reference: Neumann, Erich. *The Great Mother : An Analysis of the Archetype*. Translated by Ralph Manheim. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 2015.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to general Greek beliefs of the afterlife (the underworld or elysium) - some authors have alluded to an older tradition of sending bodies out to sea after death, or the usage of funerary boats. This is not necessarily a Greek tradition, however, it is alluded to along the Aegean and with cultures the Greeks would have had contact with.

Reference: Brody, Aaron J. "The Specialized Religions of Ancient Mediterranean Seafarers". *Religion Compass* 2, no. 4 (2008): 444-54.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Not specific to Hera's maritime cult; a generalization of the whole of early Greek polytheism beliefs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Not specific to Hera's maritime cult; a generalization of the whole of early Greek polytheism beliefs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: Not specific to Hera's maritime cult; a generalization of the whole of early Greek polytheism beliefs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Not specific to Hera's maritime cult; a generalization of the whole of early Greek polytheism beliefs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Not specific to Hera's maritime cult; a generalization of the whole of early Greek polytheism beliefs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Possible relation to burial at sea, as noted above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Speaking specifically of the cult of Maritime Hera as opposed to the whole of Greek polytheism, she would reign as one of the supreme gods in the realm, but she is not the only one. She was not believed to live in the sea or come from the sea, rather, she has practical and symbolic power over it. She shares this space with gods such as Poseidon, and other minor beings such as the sirens and nymphs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Creatures that dwell in the sea or near the sea (Scylla, Charybdis, the Sirens, etc).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: not all, but some

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, within the Greek pantheon. Within the cult of maritime Hera, it is only her, but she shares the realm with others. None seem to be more powerful than others; however, Hera does dwell in the realm of the sea, earth, marriage, fertility, environment etc, so she oversees many interrelated aspects that could be needed by a variety of people. Additionally, she is the most senior female deity in the solidified Greek pantheon and does command arguably more power/respect than other related deities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: The greek pantheon and deities specific to particular realms (i.e., the sea)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Worshippers of the cult of maritime Hera would need to adhere to the laws of the sea and carry out the proper rituals at departure and arrival, to both thank and ask the goddess for safe passage. They would also need to adhere to the proper guest-friendship protocols of Greek society, particularly at sanctuaries on harbours or near borders.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– Yes

Notes: Referring to guest-friendship protocols in Greek society.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes

Notes: The cult of maritime Hera would not deal specifically with matters of marriage and sex, however, many of the sanctuaries where Hera would have been worshipped for her maritime aspects are cross-over spots and her altars received votives of this nature (asking for fertility, sacrifices prior to marriage, etc). Some votives can be interpreted as asking for both fertility of the self and the sea.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Adultery:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Incest:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Other sexual practices:
– Yes [specify]: Sex before marriage.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

— Yes

Notes: In literature, maritime Hera does not appreciate male soldiers who 'stay by their boats.' She encourages action and prowess in battle. It can be said that this carries over to her religious worship as well.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

— Yes

Notes: At sanctuaries of maritime Hera, there is evidence of worshippers throwing conical cups into the sea as offerings, or sinking them in wells, which has been interpreted as a form of oracular practice; a sailor could determine whether the sea voyage would be successful or not by the way the cup sank or floated. There is evidence for this at Samos, Perachora, and Gravisca. It was likely an important practice and a responsibility of sailors to do this at the coastline sanctuaries of Hera and would be inappropriate not to obtain the goddess' blessing prior to embarking.

Reference: Kapitan, Gerhard. "Archaeological Evidence for Rituals and Customs on Ancient Ships". Edited by Harry Tzalas. 1st Symposium on Ship Construction in Antiquity, 1985, 147-62.

Reference: Hans, Walter, Angelika Clemente, and Wolf Dietrich Niemeier. Ursprung Und Frühzeit Des Heraion Von Samos. Samos 21,1.. Deutsches Archaologisches Institut, 2019.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

— Yes

Notes: In the way that all Greek deities sanctuaries, their votives, and architecture must be considered sacred and protected.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: There is evidence for many rituals dedicated to maritime Hera as noted previously. Additionally, there were seasonal rituals for washing and re-dressing Hera's cult statue at Argos and Samos. There was a proper time, space, offering for each ritual that was strictly adhered to by the Greeks.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: This is arguably the most important to maritime Hera, particularly for sailors who would count on Hera's granting of a safe and successful sea voyage, which they would only be granted based on proper ritual and votive offerings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: In the same way that all Greek sanctuaries required purification before entering the sacred space.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Punishment would be doled out primarily by Hera, but as she is not the only deity with power over the realm of the sea, it could come from elsewhere.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The sea itself was known as dark and unpredictable.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

Notes: Hera was known to be an ambivalent goddess. She did not always need a reason to inflict harm on mortals, particularly if they were not part of a region she was the patron deity of.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: Not by Hera

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: particularly if travelling to war/fighting in battles via or on the sea.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: The cult of maritime Hera involved not only the sea, but weather as well (wind, rain, the elements). Poor adherence to rituals could lead to severe weather while on a sea voyage. Poor weather could occur for other reasons, however, one could hope Hera would assist sea voyagers to get through the poor weather prior to embarking (i.e., by leaving votives or pouring libations). Hera was prayed to for rain in the same sanctuaries where ship votives were left behind as well, as part of her duty as a fertility goddess (fertility of both people and the environment).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: This would be the main punishment maritime Hera could dole out - disaster on sea voyages/shipwrecks.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: As with the previous question, it could be done by Hera, but also by another god with power over the sea.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: As with punishment, rewards would be doled out primarily by Hera, but as she is not the only deity with power over the realm of the sea, it could come from elsewhere.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: By the nature of the sea and weather.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Sailors could be granted with a successful sea voyage through carrying out proper rituals and devotion to maritime Hera.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: Not specifically in the maritime cult of Hera. Hera has granted 'death' in myth as a reward to heroes (Kelobis and Biton, for example) - rewarding them with ultimate kleos/glory. However, this is not necessarily something maritime Hera would be rewarding to those devoted to her in this aspect.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: On sea voyages, with fishing, with war.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes
Notes: In a way, particularly if maritime Hera was prayed to for success in colonization and the travels required for it.
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is an eschatology present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Not specific to Hera's maritime cult;

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Only sacrifice of certain objects, dedicated as votive offerings.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

To out-groups:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Destroyed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Other:

– Yes [specify]: To the deity herself, Hera

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Only the time it takes to perform rituals, which is not a prescribed set of time/frequency.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Maritime Hera could be the recipient of private/home ritual in addition to rituals at public sanctuaries.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

— Yes

Notes: While there is no written evidence attesting to specific large-scale festivals devoted to maritime Hera, many of the ones we do know of would have at least been in part celebrating this aspect of her character and religious veneration. (Particularly the annual festival at the Samian Heraion).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

— Yes

Notes: Many sanctuaries of Hera were overseen by a priestess, however, this does not apply to all, and not specifically to the maritime aspect of her religious veneration.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A country - ancient Greece

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: It can be assumed that traditions, rituals, and beliefs would have been passed down through families, but also through community connections, political offices (particularly for patron deities), and city-state friendships. This may be considered more informal education as there is no 'school' that is attested to.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Notes: Many of the larger sanctuaries of Hera kept inventories of dedications, however, they were not specific to one aspect of her worship, and it is unclear whether they could be classified as a part of taxation or not - it is unlikely.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: In general, Greek cults were subject to the same punishments set by the society of which they were a part of.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Unless they are soldiers/warriors themselves.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The languages and dialects of the regions listed above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The languages and dialects of the regions listed above.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Notes: Not specific to this cult, but rather a calendar (not fully yet understood) utilized by the widespread societies of ancient Greece. Certain sanctuaries of Hera did dictate the times of celebrations and festivals, such as the Argive Heraion whose priestesses were used as time-keepers and referred to as markers of time.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Not that would dictate this religious group's beliefs or practices.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: Not formally, however; many of the worshippers of maritime Hera would have been fishermen and would have been asking for the fertility of the sea in order to provide food for themselves (and their families or community).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Cult Sites of "Maritime Hera"

Bibliography

General References

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